

YOUTH INFO SURVEY 2025

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*MOBILITY AND THE ROLE OF YOUTH INFORMATION IN
THE LIVES OF YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR
CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS*

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

<i>1/ WHY ARE YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS IMPORTANT IN THE CONTEXT OF THE YOUTH INFO SURVEY 2025</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>2/WHAT DO YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS THINK ABOUT MOBILITY?</i>	<i>8</i>
<i>3/ HOW DO YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS LEARN ABOUT MOBILITY?</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>4/ HOW DID YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS EXPERIENCE MOBILITY IN 2022 AND 2023?</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>5/ WHAT MOBILITY CHALLENGES DO YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS IDENTIFY?</i>	<i>18</i>
<i>CONCLUSIONS</i>	<i>31</i>
<i>BIBLIOGRAPHY</i>	<i>32</i>

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Mobility preferences in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.	9
Figure 2: Experience in searching for mobility-related information in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.	10
Figure 3: Sources of mobility-related information in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.	11
Figure 4: Helpfulness and usefulness of various information types and delivery methods in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.	13
Figure 5: Online search preferences in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.	14
Figure 6: Grant support and application support in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.	17
Figure 7: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Discrimination	19
Figure 8: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Access	20
Figure 9: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Financial problems	21
Figure 10: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Discouragement from relatives	22
Figure 11: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Travel-related issues	24
Figure 12: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Health issues	25
Figure 13: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Mental health issues	26
Figure 14: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Problems with hosting institutions	27
Figure 15: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Lack of communication with relatives	29
Figure 16: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Lack of language skills	30

1/WHY ARE YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS IMPORTANT IN THE CONTEXT OF THE YOUTH INFO SURVEY 2025?

1.1/ WHAT IS THE EURODESK YOUTH INFO SURVEY 2025?

The Eurodesk Youth Info Surveys are conducted regularly in order to provide insights into the field of youth mobility information. The previous surveys were conducted in 2017 (*Sabuni 2018*), 2019 (*Sabuni 2019*), 2022 (*Bárta 2022*), and the latest one in 2024 (*Bárta 2025*).

The full report, titled Eurodesk Youth Info Survey 2025, has already been published, and we invite you to explore it online or in hard copy.

This publication does not reiterate the general findings from the main report; it focuses solely on one of the important minorities among young people: young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions. Its purpose is to identify the specific needs, experiences, and challenges they face. This is achieved by comparing the minority group, in this case, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions, with the majority youth. The majority youth are all young people who do not suffer from disabilities or chronic health conditions. Comparing these two groups shows clearly where suffering from disabilities or chronic health conditions makes a difference.

These findings aim to help youth information services better tailor their approach to this particular minority, thereby improving the delivery of information and the mobility experience of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions.

1.2/ WHO ARE YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS?

The *UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities* (United Nations 2006) is a key global document which provides a clear insight into who persons with disabilities are and what barriers they face. The UN Convention clearly states that (ibid: 4): “Persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.” It also emphasises that “everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth therein, without distinction of any kind” (ibid), stressing that any discrimination or other unequal treatment of people with disabilities goes against the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (United Nations 1948).

The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (United Nations 2006) also recognised children with disabilities as one of the key groups at risk of unequal treatment (ibid: Article 7). There are about 240 million children with disabilities worldwide, according to UNICEF (2025). In response to the challenges that disabled children and youth are facing, UNICEF (2025) introduced global initiatives focusing on reducing physical barriers (e.g. in public space or transport), communication and information barriers (e.g. in school or public announcement contexts), and attitudinal barriers (e.g. stereotyping, harassment, or bullying) that children with disabilities face.

In the European context, about 17% of all young people aged 16 to 29 years old were living with long-standing health problems or chronic illnesses, and about 10% were living with a disability in 2022 (Eurostat 2024). This is recognised in the *EU Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030* (European Commission 2021), which outlines various actions towards equality of people with disabilities, including actions explicitly aimed at young people in domains such as mobility, democracy, housing, education, and many others.

As shown above, children and young people living with disabilities or chronic health conditions have long been recognised as a particularly vulnerable group. Therefore, the Eurodesk Youth Info Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to report on their health status and collected 170 responses from young people with disabilities and 286 answers from young people living with long-term health conditions. Those two groups were merged for the purposes of this report, and they are referred to as “young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions” in this text. All in all, this report is based on responses from **401 young people who identified as living with disabilities or chronic health conditions**. All results are rounded to the nearest whole number.

2/WHAT DO YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS THINK ABOUT MOBILITY?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on mobility in general. For overall results, refer to the *main report 2025*.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions do not differ much from majority youth in general mobility preferences. They are just **as open to going abroad and to using various mobility formats and lengths** as other young people.

There is only one **minor difference** in this area: one related to internships (see Figure 1). Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are less keen to do an **internship abroad** (77% of them are very interested or interested, in comparison with 83% of the majority youth), which may be related to the specific situation they find themselves in. It may be more difficult to find an employer who would be accommodating to their specific needs, for example. Despite that, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are still interested in this option, only slightly less than the majority youth.

These are very positive results: despite the specific situation that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions find themselves in, they are keen to explore and go **abroad for mobility periods** to the same extent as their peers with no health-related complications.

¹ In the survey, 115 young people identified as living with disability (but not long-term health conditions), 231 identified as living with long-term health conditions (but not disability), and 55 identified as living with both a disability and long-term health conditions.

Figure 1: Mobility preferences in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.

3/ HOW DO YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS LEARN ABOUT MOBILITY?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on their information needs related to mobility. For overall results, see the [main report 2025](#).

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are **more experienced in searching for mobility-related information than their peers**: 80% of them have already tried searching for mobility-related information, in comparison with 76% of the majority youth (see Figure 2). This means that, on top of being just as open to the idea of going abroad for a mobility period, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are slightly more likely to seek information on the topic.

Figure 2: Experience in searching for mobility-related information in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.

Figure 3: Sources of mobility-related information in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions were slightly less likely to use schools or universities as a source of mobility-related information. 74% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions used educational institutions as an information source, in comparison with 80% of majority youth (see Figure 3). This is not a large difference, but it may be related to the fact that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions might need to look up specific information, and educational institutions might only be able to provide general information on mobility.

When we asked young people what methods of receiving information on mobility they prefer, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions found it less useful to talk to their peers (see Figure 4). While 87% of majority youth considered real stories from young people who went abroad as a very useful or useful information source, only 80% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions agreed. Similarly, while 88% of majority youth stated that they find it very useful or useful to hear from other young people who have already been abroad, only 83% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions agreed. These differences are not large, and they suggest that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions still want to hear the experiences of others. At the same time, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions know that there might be specific information they might need and that they will not learn this way.

What kind of information related to going abroad would you find helpful to receive? - Real stories from young people who went abroad?

How useful are the following methods for receiving information about mobility opportunities? - Hear from other young people who have already been abroad

Figure 4: Helpfulness and usefulness of various information types and delivery methods in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.

How do you usually find information about things that interest you / information about going abroad?

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions

Majority Youth

Figure 5: Online search preferences in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions **look for information online the same way** as the majority youth. The only slight difference is that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are **less likely to follow influencers** (see Figure 5). Only 65% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that it was very likely or likely that they would follow influencers online, in comparison with 74% of the majority youth.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions **use social media similarly** to the majority youth. The only differences are that they are **more likely to follow Facebook and Reddit** (see Figure 5). 48% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions would likely use Facebook to find mobility-related information, in comparison to 40% in majority youth. In case of Reddit, 23% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions would use it to find mobility-related information, in comparison to 12% in majority youth.

All of these results constitute only minor differences between young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and the majority youth. These differences can be useful in better reaching out to young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions, but we also see that in terms of looking up information on mobility, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions often behave very similarly to the majority youth, using the same platforms or methods of keeping up to date.

4/ HOW DID YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS EXPERIENCE MOBILITY IN 2022 AND 2023?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on their direct mobility experiences. For overall results, refer to the [*main report 2025*](#).

The detailed analyses show no differences between the young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and the majority youth in how many of them went abroad and how they rated their experience. **About 40% of them went abroad** in 2022 or 2023, **93% of them considered it to be either an amazing or a good experience**, and about **97% of them would be willing to encourage others to go** on a mobility experience of their own.

This suggests that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions were just as likely to go abroad in 2022 or 2023, and they enjoyed their stays just as much as the majority youth did. As will become evident in the next chapters, this is all an excellent result, given that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are more likely to face challenges before and during their mobility stays.

Comparisons show that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions were **more likely to use the European Solidarity Corps programme to support their stay** (17% in comparison with 11% in majority youth; see Figure 6). This is in line with the recently published evaluation of the European Solidarity Corps programme which highlighted high inclusivity of this programme (European Commission 2025).

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions were **less likely to be supported in the application process by a teacher or a professor** (see Figure 6). Only 14% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions were supported by a teacher or a professor in comparison with 20% of majority youth. This is in line with one of the previous findings: a lower likelihood of using schools as information channels by young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions. In both cases, one of the potential reasons for these results is the specificity of situations in which young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions find themselves. While educational professionals may provide general advice and guidance, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions might need more specific support.

Figure 6: Grant support and application support in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth.

5/ WHAT MOBILITY CHALLENGES DO YOUNG PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES OR CHRONIC HEALTH CONDITIONS IDENTIFY?

The Eurodesk Youth Information Survey 2025 provided young people with an opportunity to share their opinions on the challenges they faced during their mobility experience or when planning to organise it. For overall results, refer to the [*main report 2025*](#).

Since both the young people who went abroad and those who decided not to answered the questions on challenges in organising mobility stays, we can compare the results of these two groups. Those with mobility experiences were asked about challenges they faced, and those with no mobility experience were asked about challenges that prevented them from going abroad.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions **systematically report higher hurdles on their way to mobility** than their peers from majority backgrounds. The following paragraphs outline the specific differences between those two groups.

Discrimination is perceived severely by young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions (see Figure 7). 34% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported facing discrimination **in accessing mobility programmes** (in comparison with only 13% of majority youth), and 27% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions stated that discrimination **prevented them from going abroad** altogether (in comparison with only 7% in majority youth). These are striking results. **About a third of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions report discrimination in connection with mobility experiences.**

Young people who went abroad

Did you face any of the following challenges when accessing the programmes? - Discrimination (e.g. race, gender, age, disability)

Young people who did not go abroad

Did any of the following problems prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023? - Discrimination (e.g. race, gender, age, disability)

Figure 7: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Discrimination

Matching eligibility criteria, experiencing administrative issues, and lack of information were also reported to a higher extent by young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions (see Figure 8). 37% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions stated that they experienced problems with matching eligibility criteria when accessing the mobility programmes (in comparison with 23% of the majority youth). 45% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that administrative problems prevented them from going abroad altogether (in comparison with 32% of the majority youth). 38% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions agreed that they faced a lack of information when accessing the mobility programmes (in comparison with 38% of majority youth). These results suggest that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions might greatly benefit from specific support in the application phase of the mobility process.

Figure 8: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Access

Did you face any of the following challenges when accessing the programmes? - Financial problems to cover the cost

Did any of the following problems prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023? - Financial problems

Figure 9: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Financial problems

Financial problems are another area in which young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions struggle (see Figure 9). 56% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported financial difficulties in accessing the mobility programmes (in comparison with 48% of the majority youth), and 72% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that financial problems prevented them from going abroad (in comparison with 59% of the majority youth). Health difficulties often bring additional financial costs to living, and these need to be covered abroad just as well as at home. These results show that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions struggle with these costs in the mobility context.

Did you face any of the following challenges when accessing the programmes? - Discouragement from my family

Did any of the following problems prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023? - Discouragement from my family

Did you face any of the following challenges when accessing the programmes? - Discouragement from my friends

Did any of the following problems prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023? - Discouragement from my friends

- a) Strongly agree
- b) Agree
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

Figure 10: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Discouragement from relatives

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are also **more likely to be discouraged from going abroad by their families and friends** (see Figure 10). 30% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported that their families discouraged them from going abroad when accessing the mobility programmes (in comparison with 19% of the majority youth), and 31% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that discouragement from their families prevented them from going abroad (in comparison with 21% of the majority youth). Furthermore, 29% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions told us that they were discouraged from going abroad by their friends (in comparison with 13% in majority youth), and 13% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that discouragement from friends prevented them from going abroad altogether (in comparison with 9% in majority youth).

These are, again, findings with serious implications. Preparing, organising, and undergoing a mobility period abroad is no small undertaking for young people. Discouragement from their closest, especially in vulnerable youth such as young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions, may undermine what could become a highly positive life experience from ever taking place. **Information efforts should also focus on families of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions** to increase the chances of them being supported in pursuing their mobility experience, not being discouraged from it.

Did you face any of the following challenges when accessing the programmes? - Difficulties to travel abroad

Did any of the following reasons prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023? - Travel-related problems

Figure 11: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Travel-related issues

Travelling itself can be a demanding exercise for young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions, and it is among the challenges they face more profoundly than their peers (see Figure 11). 35% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions stated that they faced difficulties in travelling abroad (in comparison with 24% of majority youth), and 33% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions told us that travel-related problems completely prevented them from going abroad (in comparison with 24% of the majority youth). While specific travel support may be needed for young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions, information support is key to lowering this barrier for them. Such support may include information on the specific grant options available to help young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions during their travels, as well as the assistance that sending and receiving organisations can offer.

Health problems themselves may be a challenge for young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions (see Figure 12). 35% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported **long-term health problems to be one of the general difficulties they faced** during their mobility stay (in comparison with 9% of the majority youth), and 52% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that they **faced specific physical health problems** during their mobility stay (in comparison with 26% of the majority youth). Moreover, 49% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported that physical health issues **prevented them from going abroad** (in comparison with 9% of the majority youth). Physical health is an enormously important topic for young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions. **Specific information should be readily available** for them, for example, on how to register with a general practitioner in the host country, how to set up appropriate medical insurance, and so on.

Figure 12: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Health issues

Did you face any of the following difficulties when moving or living abroad?- Mental health problems during the stay

Did any of the following reasons prevent you from going abroad in 2022 or 2023? - Mental health issues

Figure 13: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Mental health issues

Mental health issues were also reported to be significant challenges for young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions (see Figure 13). 54% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said that they encountered mental health problems during their stay abroad (in comparison with 25% of majority youth), and 47% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions stated that mental health issues prevented them from going abroad in the first place (in comparison with 18% of majority youth). The mental health of young people has been deteriorating globally and deserves special attention, especially in demanding circumstances, such as going abroad. **Information on this topic should be accessible to all young people**, with a particular emphasis on actively offering it to vulnerable youth, including those with disabilities or chronic health conditions.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions also more **often faced problems with a hosting institution** (see Figure 14). 35% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported having problems with a hosting institution during their stay (in comparison with 20% of majority youth), and 21% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions stated that problems with a hosting institution prevented them from going abroad completely (in comparison with 13% in majority youth). **Hosting institutions should be provided with ample information on how to support** young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions in their mobility stays to prevent challenging situations.

Figure 14: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Problems with hosting institutions

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions also **more often reported challenges in their social lives** during the mobility stays (see Figure 15). 28% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions told us that they **lacked communication with their families** (in comparison with 16% in majority youth), another 34% suffered from lack of communication **with their friends** (in comparison with 23% in majority youth), 37% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions said they **did not have enough leisure time activities** during their stays (in comparison with 24% in majority youth), and finally 33% of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions reported **difficulties in adapting to a new culture** during their mobility stays (in comparison with 21% of majority youth). It is apparent that while to some young people, it may be evident that they will need to be more active in managing their social lives, to others, it may be more challenging. **Information services can support young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions in managing their social lives,** and their peers in actively supporting them during their mobility period.

Did you face any of the following difficulties when moving or living abroad?

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions

Majority Youth

Figure 15: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Lack of communication with relatives

Did you face any of the following difficulties when moving or living abroad?

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions

Figure 16: Challenges in organising mobility stays in young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions and majority youth: Lack of language skills

Finally, **lack of understanding** of how things work abroad is more challenging to young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions (43% in comparison with 26% in majority youth), and young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions were also more likely to suffer from lack of language skills (45% in comparison with 33% in majority youth; see Figure 16).

All in all, this chapter extensively shows that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions report systematically higher on various barriers they are facing when implementing their mobility stays. These challenges range from discrimination, through health-related issues, social aspects, and various practicalities. It is obvious that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions should be provided with specific information in order to mitigate these challenges.

CONCLUSIONS

This report shows that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are **just as enthusiastic about going abroad as their peers**. Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions also enjoy their stays to the same extent, and they rate their mobility experiences as positively as their peers.

Young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are **even more likely to look up mobility-related information than their peers**. However, they have slightly different preferences in seeking information. Educational institutions, influencers, or hearing about the mobility experiences of others are not seen as useful by young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions as they are by their peers. This may be connected to the fact that their mobility experience will likely differ from that of the majority youth, and young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are aware of that.

Despite these positive results, further analyses showed that young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are **more likely to face numerous challenges related to mobility**. Issues such as discrimination, administrative hurdles, a lack of information, financial costs associated with mobility, discouragement from family and friends, and many others. All of them are reported more often by young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions than by the majority youth.

Mobilities undertaken by young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions are a story of **resilience**. Faced with many challenges and barriers, young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions **still manage to go abroad and enjoy their stays to the same extent as their peers**. While this is undoubtedly a success story, youth information services may **help prepare future generations of young people with disabilities or chronic health conditions for their mobility stays even better**: being ready for the challenges, better at dealing with them, and eventually having even more positive mobility experiences.

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